

Study of Social Media Adoption as a Leverage to Marketing Strategies by Organizations in India

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Abstract: Social media can emerge as a powerful tool if strategically leveraged. This quantitative study explores the factors leading to the strategic adoption of social media and the leverage it provides to the marketing strategies of the organization.

The study adopted a survey questionnaire approach to collect 342 responses from the top and mid-level managers who are decision-makers or use social media for marketing in organizations in India. The data was analyzed using Structural Equation Modelling in AMOS 23.

This research discusses the influence of top management, social media perceived usefulness (SMPU), social media communication, and social media perceived playfulness (SMPP) on social media adoption. Social media interactions do not directly influence social media adoption. The study identified a mediating role of SMPU between SMPP and social media adoption. A strong impact of social media adoption is confirmed on product development and improvement and marketing communications.

The findings of this research can enable marketing practitioners to strategic adoption of social media and ensure alignment of their efforts with the customer needs and organizational objectives. Big data from social media clubbed with AI could reveal the psychographic characteristics of customers that can be valuable in customer engagement and innovation.

The study extends the Uses & Gratification theory at the organizational level. It also throws some interesting results of interplay between the constructs of two theories.

Keywords: Social Media Adoption, Social Media, TOE, TAM, Uses and Gratification, Social Media Marketing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pocket-friendly Smartphones, easy-to-use technology and, the social benefit of staying connected with family and friends can be the key reasons for the increasing popularity of social media with the masses. Organizations are finding it hard to ignore social media when it has such wide acceptance by their target customers.

Social media can emerge as a powerful tool for organizations if leveraged strategically. While social media platforms offer touchpoints for organizations to have meaningful, real-time engagement with their customers (Gruber et al., 2015), its adoption should be congruent and aligned with the needs of social media users (Zhu and Chen, 2015) and their organizational objectives.

A study of social media marketing in India by Ernst & Young revealed that an increasing number of organizations in India are embracing social media to attract, engage, and transact with their customers. As per the Ernst & Young report (www.ey.com, 2016), the top three objectives for the social media presence of the companies were to create awareness, build a community, and engage with customers. As a growing number of organizations in India adopt social media, it is important to understand the factors that influence social media adoption and the leverage the organizations draw from these platforms for their marketing strategies.

At a conceptual level, there is no dispute that social media can be used by companies to create marketing strategies for brand management, e.g. (Jin, 2012; Laroche et al., 2013) and collaborative product development, e.g. (Mangold and Faulds, 2009; Porter and Donthu, 2008). Parveen, Jaafar & Ainin (2015), while investigating the role of social media in marketing, found that it had utilization in many areas such as advertising, promotion, branding, searching information, and customer relationship building. Also, there is tremendous potential in social media as a resource for innovation and new product development by developing customer insights, accessing knowledge, co-creating ideas with users, and supporting new product launches (Roberts and Piller, 2016).

But with great potential comes big risks. While the usage of social media by marketers is growing, their biggest fear is the consumer backlash on social media and negative feeds going viral. These could result in bad press, falling stocks, tarnishing of brand image, and in extreme cases, businesses shutting down (Grégoire et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2016). For this reason, precisely, organizations need to invest in social media after careful consideration and setting strategic objectives for this medium. Also, social media cannot be a stand-alone activity within an organization and should be integrated with the rest of the business processes of the company.

Rathore et al. (2016) suggested in their research that “to gain potential value from social media mining and social media analytics, businesses need to put in place a systematic approach to support business intelligence workflows”. With the growing advancement in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning, it is becoming possible to leverage big data from social media for precise personalization, customer engagement, and product/services improvement and development.

While it is important to know the business leverage for which a company will adopt social media, it is equally important to understand the factors that lead to the selection of social media platforms by organizations. The objective of this study is to identify factors that lead to social media adoption and its leverage on the marketing strategies of organizations in India.

This paper is organized into seven sections. In section 2, the theoretical background is discussed in detail. This will be followed by sections 3, 4, and 5 on the research model and hypotheses, methodology, and result and analysis. Section 6, discussion, presents the findings of the data analysis and finally, section 7, the conclusion, summarizes the contribution of the research and limitations of the study.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

While there are a fair number of researches on social media adoption from an individual's viewpoint, from the organization's perspective, research is limited. Using theories of Uses and Gratification (U&G), Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE), and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), this paper creates a model for social media adoption by organizations and its leverage on their marketing strategies.

TAM explains users' acceptance patterns of computer information systems (Davis, 1989). It has since then been used to study the acceptance of many new technologies. Perceived usefulness has emerged as the major determinant of computer acceptance in the workplace. However, beyond perceived usefulness, playfulness may also have a significant effect on technology acceptance (Li et al., 2005; Nysveen et al., 2005).

From an individual's perspective, in the past, TAM has been largely utilized to investigate scenarios for different social media technologies, e.g. (Rauniar et al., 2013; Siamagka et al., 2015). Using TAM, Rauniar et al. (2013) researched the user attitude and usage behavior of social media sites to develop future understandings and deployment of social media.

Despite several studies on technology acceptance that are grounded in TAM, studies available for social media adoption from an organization's perspective are limited. While Siamagka et al. (2015) discovered perceived usefulness as the most significant driver of social media adoption by B2B organizations, this study explores the role of perceived usefulness and

perceived playfulness in the adoption of social media by organizations and also evaluates the relationship of perceived usefulness with perceived playfulness and social media interaction.

TOE framework has been successfully applied to numerous technologies like EDI, e.g. (Kuan and Chau, 2001), enterprise systems, e.g. (Ramdani et al., 2009), Internet, e.g. (Tan and Teo, 1998), and e-Commerce, e.g. (Liu, 2008). Researchers found limited material on social media adoption from the organizational perspective that was grounded in the TOE framework.

Even though social media is deceptively easy to use, its adoption can only be leveraged if the pros and cons of social media implementation are discussed and strategized at the organization level. Hence the role of top management support needs investigation. This research attempts to understand the contribution of top management in making social media a strategic part of the firm's marketing function.

U&G theory has largely been used to identify the psychological needs that prompt individuals to look for media that address their needs (Lariscy et al., 2011). Though originally, U&G theory was developed to examine traditional media, e.g. (Kippax and Murray, 1980; Rubin, 1983), due to its interactive nature, the Internet and social media lend themselves to a U&G approach, e.g. (Grant, 2005; Whiting and Williams, 2013; Gan, 2016). It is important to note that the study of U&G theory for social media has largely been to identify the gratifications individuals seek from using social media, e.g. (Ku et al., 2013; Alhabash et al., 2014).

Dunne et al. (2010) applied the U&G theory to investigate digital natives' motives for using social networking sites. He identified seven gratifications sought from social networking, including communication, friending, identity creation and management, entertainment, escapism and alleviation of boredom, information search, and social interaction (Dunne et al., 2010). Whiting et al. (2013), in studying social media adoption by individuals, identified key U&G themes of social interaction, information seeking, pass time, entertainment, relaxation, communication, convenience, expression of opinions, and information sharing.

However, from an organization's perspective, U&G theory has not been applied to study the gratifications a firm may seek while using social media for its marketing function. This research paper looks at the importance of interaction and communication as gratifications influencing the adoption of social media by the marketing teams.

Extant research indicates that new technology, on its introduction, is studied for theories of TAM and TOE. While there are studies, based on using TAM and TOE, on social media adoption by individuals, there is limited research from an organizational perspective using these theories. Also, the researchers did not come across any study on social media adoption by organizations based on U&G theory. This research attempts to bridge this gap and present a model to study the factors that lead to social media adoption by organizations and the leverage of this adoption for two marketing constructs - marketing communication, and product and service development and improvement.

3. RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES

Based on the literature review and theoretical background, the study evaluates the influence of social media perceived usefulness, social media perceived playfulness, top management support, social media interaction, and social media communication in the adoption of social media by a firm for its marketing strategies. The research considers social media adoption by business to be for strategic gains like increasing the customer base and addressing the competitive pressure. The psychological concept of social influence is grounded in the assumption that the behavior and presence of others heavily influences a person's behavior (Rauniar et al., 2013). The characteristics of social media rooted in user-generated content and interactivity indicate that the greater the number of people using social media, the higher will be its value and influence. So, it is important to evaluate the increase in the number of customers reached through the adoption of a social media platform. Lin & Lin (2008) defined competitive pressure as a pressure that comes from a threat of losing competitive advantage and forces firms to adopt and diffuse e-business. Researchers have agreed that intense competitive pressure is an important determinant of IT adoption (Kuan and Chau, 2001; Zhu and Chen, 2015; Ramdani et al., 2009). This research assesses social media adoption through the competitive pressure experienced by the organization to implement social media and the expected expansion of critical mass from social media usage.

The marketing strategies considered for this research include marketing communication related to advertising, direct marketing, special offer promotions, brand updates, and data insights-driven new product/service development and improvement of the existing offerings.

Fig. 1 shows the conceptual model for this study. And Appendix 1 gives a summary of all the constructs and measurement items and their key references.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Model

Top Management Support

Top Management of an organization can influence technology innovation and adoption by allocating sufficient and timely resources (Annukka, 2008) and supporting change (Premkumar and Michael, 1995). Tiago and Verissimo [2014] found "facilitation of top-down directives" to be a key factor influencing the effective utilization of digital media for marketing purposes. Resources, directives, and processes provided by the top management to successfully utilize social media for the company’s marketing strategies define the top management support. So, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis One: Top Management Support will positively impact the adoption of Social Media

Social Media Perceived Usefulness

Social media's perceived usefulness signifies the benefits the managers would enjoy by adopting social media into their marketing function. The relationship between perceived usefulness and intention to use technology is based on the idea that people may adopt technology to improve the performance of their work (Lorenzo-Romero et al., 2014). Rauniar et al. (2013) defined perceived usefulness for social media as “the extent to which the social media user believes that using a particular social media site helps to meet the related goal-driven needs of the individual”. While Rauniar et al. (2013) based his study from an individual’s viewpoint, this research takes the perspective of an organization to assess the perceived usefulness of social media. Here, social media perceived usefulness represents the advantages of performance improvement of the firm’s staff, increased customer engagement, improved decision making, and staying informed about the competitors’ presence on social media. So, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis Two: Social Media Perceived Usefulness will positively impact the adoption of Social Media

Social Media Perceived Playfulness

Individuals consider playfulness, an element of fun, provided by the social media platform as an important factor while selecting a social media platform, e.g. (Li et al., 2005; Nysveen et al., 2005). Through this study, researchers wanted to confirm whether firms consider the playfulness of a social media platform while adopting it for their marketing. *Social media playfulness reflects the entertainment and fun element that organizations can introduce in their communication and interactions on social media platforms.*

Rauniar et al. (2013) defined perceived playfulness of social media to be the "extent to which the social media-related activities are perceived to be fun by individuals". Contests, games, and other entertainment forms are likely to heighten users' interest and engagement with a brand on social channels (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). Hence, the organizational ability to provide playfulness in their engagement on social media with their audience may be a factor for the adoption of the platform by them.

Increased frequency in customer visits to a social media page because of the entertainment and playfulness experienced there would give the marketers greater data points on their customers. This could help them in understanding their customers better and enhance the product/service experience for them. In this scenario, social media perceived usefulness could play a mediating role between social media perceived playfulness and social media adoption. So, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis Three: Social Media Perceived Playfulness will positively impact the Adoption of Social Media

Hypothesis Four: Social Media Perceived Playfulness will positively impact Social Media Perceived Usefulness

Hypothesis Five: Social Media Perceived Usefulness will mediate the effect of Social Media Perceived Playfulness on Social Media Adoption

Social Media Interaction

Social media interaction is a two-way process that characterizes the interactions of customers with the organization and with other customers to generate traction, feedback, and insights (Goldfarb and Tucker, 2011). The interactions with customers may be a key theme of gratification for organizations. The user-generated content collected from these interactions and the resultant insights could increase customer engagement and improve decision making and product/service innovation. Here too, social media perceived usefulness could be a mediator in the influence of social media interaction on social media adoption. So, the following hypotheses are proposed:

Hypothesis Six: Social Media Interaction will positively impact the adoption of Social Media

Hypothesis Seven: Social Media Interaction will positively impact Social Media Perceived Usefulness

Hypothesis Eight: Social Media Perceived Usefulness will mediate the effect of Social Media Interaction on Social Media Adoption

Social Media Communication

Social media communication is a one-way communication from the organization to its target customers and signifies the information shared by the organization with its customers. Instant and direct communication of brand-related information and ideas could be a key gratification the organization may seek on a social media platform. According to Badea (2014), firms employed social media tools to announce, contact, educate, and connect with their customers and prospects. A steady flow of communication can help in keeping a positive company image. So, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis Nine: Social Media Communication will positively impact the adoption of Social Media

Product and Service Development and Improvement

Product and service development and improvement refer to the introduction of new products or improvements to the existing ones as an attempt to respond to customer feedback or changing consumer tastes. With consumers becoming comfortable in using social media, a growing percentage of them are using social platforms to complain, give suggestions and feedback about the company (Gesenhues, 2013), thus giving the organization customer data insights. These insights enable the firms to more holistically address customer attitudes, needs, and sentiments (He and Yan, 2014) through product and service development or improvement. So, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis Ten: Social Media Adoption will positively impact the Product and Service Development and Improvement

Marketing Communication

Marketing communication is the information the organization shares with its customers about its brand and products and services. Mangold and Faulds (2009) had proposed that social media could assist in transforming the firm's marketing

communication strategies by "shifting ways in which companies reach their target" and be present where their audience is. Given this context, social media adoption by the organization will positively impact the marketing communication of the company. The above arguments form the premise for the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis Eleven: Social Media Adoption will positively impact Marketing Communication

4. METHODOLOGY

Instrument Development

As the objective of this study was to know what factors play an important role in the adoption of social media, a quantitative research methodology was followed. A research questionnaire was administered to senior and middle management professionals associated with marketing from organizations in India.

The research questionnaire used both nominal and ordinal scales to capture responses. The nominal scale determined the respondent’s demographics and organizational details. Items for the questionnaire were either adapted from the work of previous researchers or new items were created wherever relevant, similar items could not be identified from previous research. The six-point Likert scale was used in this research to measure the responses.

Ten professionals, each with over 3 years of experience, evaluated the questionnaire for content validity by checking for redundancy and ambiguity. They also gave feedback on the sequence of questions, word choice, and measures for further refining the questionnaire. Based on their feedback, the language of certain questions was changed while the redundant questions were dropped from the final questionnaire.

Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted to check for the construct validity of the questionnaire before administering it to a larger audience. Fifty responses to the questionnaire were collected in the same environment as proposed for the main research. Preliminary analysis was successfully done on the data collected to check the reliability of the survey instrument. The values of Cronbach’s alpha for all variables were high and between the range of 0.835 and 0.940. Hence it was decided to proceed with the survey without any changes.

Sample and Data Collection

Gerbing & Anderson (1992) and Kline (2011) suggest a sample size of at least 200 for a robust SEM model. Given this recommendation, a target of a minimum of 300 good responses was set. The coverage of surveyed organizations was maximized by taking one response per organization.

The questionnaire was loaded on Google Forms and the form link circulated to prospective respondents. E-mails, LinkedIn, and professional WhatsApp groups were extensively used to share, and follow-up on the survey questionnaire. As most respondents were senior professionals and always on the move because of their job responsibilities, communication medium of e-mail and social media was effective and saved time. Out of 1020 questionnaires circulated, 342 good responses were collected with a response rate of 33.5%.

Table I and Table II give the sample characteristics. SPSS 20 and AMOS 23 were used to analyze the data.

TABLE: I

Sample Distribution				
Organization Age	Organization Size		Frequency	%
	500 or fewer employees	501 and more employees		
Established in 2004 or earlier	28	137	165	48.2
Established in 2005 or later	113	64	177	51.8
Frequency	141	201	342	
%	41.2	58.8		

TABLE: II

Sample Distribution Based on Industry	
Industry	Number of Organizations
Banking & Financial Services	24
Construction and Real Estate	23
Consumer Goods	26
Education	23
Healthcare	10
Hospitality	25
Information Technology	42
Insurance	12
Manufacturing	37
Media	27
Retail	46
Transportation, Travel, Tourism	31
Others	16

Note: 'Others' includes Agritech, Consultancy, Telecommunications, Utilities, Performing Arts

5. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Scale Reliability and Factor Analysis

The internal consistency and overall reliability of the questionnaire were tested using Cronbach's alpha. As the results from Table III show, all the constructs met the reliability criteria of values greater than 0.70 (Hair et al., 1995).

Next, factor analysis was done on scale items using principal component analysis and varimax rotation. Data having a KMO value greater than 0.50, with Bartlett's Test of Sphericity result significant at $p < 0.05$, is considered suitable to perform factor analysis [31]. The suitability of the sample for conducting factor analysis was confirmed by the KMO value of 0.927, with Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, significant as $p < 0.001$ (Table IV).

TABLE: III

Reliability Values of Latent Constructs		
Latent Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
SMI	.831	4
SMC	.854	4
SMPU	.895	4
SMPP	.880	3
TMS	.872	4
SMAPT	.790	3
MC	.897	5
PSDI	.902	6

TABLE: IV

KMO statistics and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.927
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8274.672
	df	528
	Sig.	0.000

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Kaiser's criterion of Eigenvalues greater than one was used to extract eight factors. Factor extraction details are as presented in Table V. Further analysis found that 72.56 percent variance could be explained by these eight factors, with 40.17% variance explained by the first factor.

TABLE: V

Rotated Component Matrix								
	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
PSDI5	.803	.218	-.019	.148	.104	.128	.178	.096
PSDI4	.771	.172	.056	.144	.144	.128	.179	.179
PSDI6	.753	.248	.043	.081	.119	.076	.180	.103
PSDI3	.703	.154	.294	.046	.140	.163	.037	.070
PSDI2	.663	.159	.303	.220	.101	.260	.058	.108
PSDI1	.626	.121	.308	.308	.087	.323	.130	.069
MC4	.250	.792	.229	.153	.108	.240	.123	.114
MC2	.175	.771	.210	.200	.127	.156	.185	.060
MC1	.142	.739	.256	.152	.109	.177	.124	.269
MC3	.301	.669	.233	.081	.087	.225	.085	.083
MC5	.339	.622	.124	.240	.154	.100	.156	.100
SMPU4	.129	.220	.827	.126	.167	.102	.210	.129
SMPU2	.196	.182	.744	.151	.198	.030	.144	.162
SMPU1	.192	.226	.733	.137	.142	.113	.157	.202
SMPU3	.085	.284	.674	.196	.131	.157	.262	.041
SMC4	.183	.133	.092	.834	.126	.077	.054	.115
SMC1	.114	.254	.201	.765	.141	.214	.100	.135
SMC2	.183	.192	.195	.730	.146	.229	.111	.169
SMC3	.148	.085	.095	.627	.216	.072	.257	.051
SMI2	.161	.141	.139	.132	.828	.175	.119	.013
SMI1	.064	.111	.214	.159	.775	.205	.066	.033
SMI4	.112	.117	.197	.070	.738	.218	.144	.038
SMI3	.139	.046	.014	.160	.717	-.021	.023	.068
TMS1	.261	.128	.165	.189	.140	.783	.116	.116
TMS4	.258	.225	.240	.202	.126	.713	.030	.102
TMS2	.126	.256	.025	.130	.214	.679	.130	.256
TMS3	.215	.259	-.015	.101	.253	.667	.307	.129
SMPP2	.218	.171	.169	.217	.141	.093	.778	.046
SMPP1	.201	.202	.246	.164	.068	.155	.768	.143
SMPP3	.192	.139	.338	.090	.161	.201	.752	.140
SMAPT2	.090	.098	.078	.093		.153	.125	.850
SMAPT3	.231	.213	.231	.252	.156	.105	-.036	.705
SMAPT1	.222	.171	.271	.130	.043	.257	.250	.631

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

A measurement model was developed using AMOS V23.0 and the Maximum Likelihood Method. Three items were

removed due to inflated chi-square and redundancy to get a good measurement model fit. This is an acceptable practice especially when new scale items are used in the study (Hair et al., 2009).

The measurement model fit assessment results revealed that its fit indices met all their threshold values and the measurement model was a good fit (Table VI).

TABLE: VI

Measurement Model Goodness of Fit Indices					
Type of Fit Measure	Name of Fit Index	Abbreviation	Results of Model Fit	Acceptable Threshold Levels	References
	Chi-square		780.445		
	Degrees of Freedom		387		
	Sig.		0.000		
Absolute Fit Measure	Normal Chi-Square	χ^2/df	2.017	1.0 < χ^2/df < 5.0	Wheaton <i>et al</i> , 1977
	Root Mean Squared Error	RMSEA	0.055	< 0.06	Browne and Cudeck, 1992, Hu and Bentler, 1999
	P-Close		0.085		
	Standardized Root Mean Square Residual	SRMR	0.0497	< 0.08	Hu and Bentler, 1999
Incremental Fit Measure	Incremental Fit Index	IFI	0.945	≥ 0.90	Bollen, 1990
	Comparative Fit Index	CFI	0.945	≥ 0.90	Hu and Bentler, 1999
	Tucker Lewis Index	TLI	0.938	≥ 0.90	Tucker & Lewis, 1973

Reliability and Validity

Once the goodness of fit of the measurement model was confirmed, it was tested for reliability and validity. Results indicate (Table VII) that the factor loading for all measurement items, except for one (SMI3), exceeded 0.6 (Byrne, 2009) and was significant. As SMI3 belonged to the social media interaction construct having only four items, the measure was retained for further analysis (Kline, 2011).

Values for item reliability were also found to be > 0.4 (Bollen, 1989) for all but three items, where the values were 0.314, 0.371, and 0.381 respectively. Though these items did not meet the criteria of $R^2 > 0.4$, taking reference from previous studies, e.g. (Han et al., 2007), these items were retained for the fit indices' assessment. Table VIII gives the construct validity results. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all variables was above the suggested value of 0.50 (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). Composite reliability values for all latent constructs were also > 0.70 (Hair et al., 2009). Table VIII confirms that the absolute values of correlations between the pairs of latent constructs were found to be less than the square of the AVEs, thus confirming the strong evidence of discriminant validity among the latent constructs.

TABLE: VII

Item Validity			
Constructs and Indicators	SFL	Critical Ratio	R ²
Top management support			
TMS1	0.837	16.949	0.701
TMS2	0.752	14.821	0.565
TMS3	0.791	15.796	0.625
TMS4	0.803	---	0.645
Social Media Perceived Playfulness			
SMPP1	0.853	20.170	0.727
SMPP2	0.8	18.311	0.64

SMPP3	0.895	---	*	0.801
Social Media Perceived Usefulness				
SMPU1	0.840	16.493		0.706
SMPU2	0.802	15.606		0.643
SMPU3	0.942	18.595		0.887
SMPU4	0.76	---	*	0.577
Social Media Communication				
SMC1	0.879	17.520		0.772
SMC2	0.849	16.912		0.721
SMC3	0.609	11.419		0.371
SMC4	0.789	---	*	0.623
Social Media Interaction				
SMI1	0.830	15.496		0.688
SMI2	0.905	16.545		0.819
SMI3	0.560	10.125		0.314
SMI4	0.755	---	*	0.570
Social Media Adoption				
SMAPT1	0.951	---	*	0.905
SMAPT2	0.617	9.349		0.381
Marketing Communication				
MC1	0.835	---	*	0.697
MC2	0.839	19.046		0.704
MC3	0.764	16.509		0.583
MC4	0.928	22.326		0.861
MC5	0.724	15.287		0.524
Product and Services Development and Improvement				
PSDI1	0.837	---	*	0.701
PSDI2	0.787	18.706		0.620
PSDI4	0.714	12.769		0.510
PSDI5	0.692	12.323		0.479

TABLE: VIII

Measurement Model Validity Results												
	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR (H)	PSDI	SMI	SMC	SMPU	TMS	SMPP	MC	SMAPT
PSDI	0.844	0.577	0.536	0.856	0.760							
SMI	0.853	0.598	0.304	0.895	0.486	0.773						
SMC	0.866	0.622	0.424	0.892	0.651	0.485	0.788					
SMPU	0.904	0.703	0.410	0.931	0.585	0.475	0.524	0.839				
TMS	0.874	0.634	0.536	0.877	0.732	0.551	0.601	0.497	0.796			
SMPP	0.886	0.723	0.410	0.894	0.621	0.442	0.516	0.640	0.572	0.850		
MC	0.911	0.674	0.460	0.930	0.678	0.442	0.591	0.624	0.665	0.571	0.821	
SMAPT	0.775	0.643	0.333	0.910	0.576	0.294	0.489	0.525	0.577	0.558	0.539	0.802

Note: CR: Composite Reliability, AVE: Average Variance Extracted, MSV: Maximum Shared Variance, MaxR(H): Maximum Reliability

MC: Marketing Communication, PSDI: Product and Services Development and Improvement, TMS: Top management support

SMPU: Social Media Perceived Usefulness, SMC: Social Media Communication, SMI: Social Media Interaction

SMPP: Social Media Perceived Playfulness, SMAPT: Social Media Adoption

Structural Model and Hypotheses Testing

The measurement model was converted to a structural model using Amos 23. Overall, the model was a good fit with acceptable indices values - Table IX gives the results of the structural model.

To test the different model relationships, regression coefficients, critical ratios (CR > 1.96), and their degree of significance

(p-value < 0.001) were examined. Based on these indicators, Hypothesis One was confirmed as results indicated top management support to have a positive and strong impact on social media adoption ($\beta = 0.503, p < .001$). Hypothesis Two was accepted as social media perceived usefulness had a positive and significant influence on social media adoption ($\beta = 0.302, p < 0.001$).

Hypothesis Three suggesting that social media perceived playfulness positively influences social media adoption was significant ($\beta = 0.182, p < 0.01$). Hypothesis Four was accepted as social media perceived playfulness had a positive and strong influence on social media perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.539, p < 0.001$). Hypothesis Five indicated the mediating role of social media perceived usefulness in the effect of Social media perceived playfulness on social media adoption. So, to confirm that it was mediation and not a case of three direct effects being individually significant, a significance test for mediation was performed using the Bootstrapping option of AMOS 23. The results (Table X) yielded a significant indirect effect for social media playfulness on social media adoption via social media perceived usefulness (coefficient = 0.153, $p < 0.001$).

Hypothesis Six, suggesting that social media interaction positively influences social media adoption was found to be statistically insignificant ($\beta = - 0.076, CR = - 1.469, p = 0.142$). Hypothesis Seven, however, confirmed that social media interaction positively influences social media perceived usefulness as this relationship was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.244, p < 0.001$). Hypothesis Eight had hypothesized a mediating role of social media perceived usefulness in the effect of Social media interaction on social media adoption. As Hypothesis Six was rejected and the direct path between social media interaction and social media adoption was not significant, there was no case for mediation in this relationship, confirming that Hypothesis Eight was not supported.

TABLE: IX

Structural Model Goodness of Fit Indices					
Type of Fit Measure	Name of Fit Index	Abbreviation	Results of Model Fit	Acceptable Threshold Levels	References
	Chi-square		780.445		
	Degrees of Freedom		387		
	Sig.		0.000		
Absolute Fit Measure	Normal Chi-Square	χ^2/df	2.017	$1.0 < \chi^2/df < 5.0$	Wheaton et al, 1977
	Root Mean Squared Error	RMSEA	0.055	< 0.06	Browne & Cudeck, 1992, Hu and Bentler, 1999
	P-Close Standardized Root Mean Square Residual	SRMR	0.0497	< 0.08	Hu and Bentler, 1999
	Incremental Fit Measure	Incremental Fit Index	IFI	0.945	≥ 0.90
	Comparative Fit Index	CFI	0.945	≥ 0.90	Hu and Bentler, 1999
	Tucker Lewis Index	TLI	0.938	≥ 0.90	Tucker & Lewis, 1973

TABLE: X

Mediation Results			
Hypotheses	Direct Effect SMPP --> SMAPT	Indirect Effect	Result
SMPP --> SMPU --> SMAPT	0.184*	0.153***	Partial Mediation

Note: Significant at: ***= p<0.001; *=p<0.05

SMPP: Social Media Perceived Playfulness; SMPU: Social Media Perceived Usefulness; SMAPT: Social Media Adoption

Hypothesis Nine, indicating a positive impact of social media communication on social media adoption, was statistically

significant ($\beta = 0.243, p < 0.001$). Similarly, Hypothesis Ten and Hypothesis Eleven confirmed a positive and strong impact of social media adoption on product and service development and improvement and marketing communication (with $\beta = 0.835, 0.791$, at $p < 0.001$).

Fig. 2 gives the output of the structural model. The results indicate that all the independent variables, i.e. top management support, social media perceived usefulness, social media perceived playfulness, and social media communication, accounted for 90% of the total variance in the decision to adopt social media ($R^2 = 0.90$). Social media perceived playfulness and social media interaction accounted for 47% of the total variance ($R^2 = 0.42$) in social media perceived usefulness. The impact of social media adoption for marketing communication accounted for 63% of the total variance ($R^2 = 0.63$). For product and service development and improvement, social media adoption accounted for 63% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.70$).

Fig 2. Structural Model Result

6. DISCUSSION

Top management support plays an important role in the strategic adoption of social media. It influences the creating of strategy for social media adoption, setting up clear social media roles and responsibilities, and providing timely resources for the social media function to perform successfully. For higher customer engagement levels and sales, it is critical to integrate the social media processes with the other back end processes of the business. Having a social media strategy and a well-defined social media organization structure could also allow the top management to take calculated risks for competitive advantage.

The research indicates that chances of social media adoption increase if managers see a benefit in using social media platforms. Results show that organizations surveyed found social media to improve the performance of their marketing teams and enabled them to stay connected with their customers, improve their own decision making, and be informed about their competition's social media initiatives.

If the visitors find the content on the organization's social media platforms entertaining and exciting, they will be more receptive to the company's marketing efforts (Papasolomou and Melanthiou, 2015). An organization's use of games, quizzes, contests, and other forms of entertainment on social media platforms is likely to heighten users' interest, participation, and make them more amenable to the company's marketing efforts (Mangold and Faulds, 2009; Papasolomou and Melanthiou, 2015). Large datasets of user-generated content on social media platforms can be analyzed using artificial intelligence tools. The analysis of data collected from social media reveals insights to marketers about their needs, preferences, attitudes, and behaviors (Martínez et al., 2016), thus increasing the usefulness of social media sites for the firm. The mediating role of social media perceived usefulness validates the influence of social media perceived playfulness in increasing the use of social media for the firm.

Previous studies had observed that social media interaction presents a strong opportunity for customers and companies to

come together and make social media a more effective marketing tool than traditional media, e.g. (Rifkin, 2000; Lim, 2010). However, the current research found the relationship between social media interaction and the adoption of social media platforms by organizations to be insignificant. For individuals, the ability to interact and stay connected with their friends and family on social media platforms could be a strong motivator for its adoption. But for the organizations in India, interactions with customers may not be a strong reason to adopt social media. In an attempt to control the outcome of interaction and collect customers' useful insights, the organization may only allow the followers to comment on the posts uploaded by the company.

This research identified social media interaction to be a strong predictor variable for social media perceived usefulness, indicating that for the organizations, the perceived usefulness of social media increased with an increase in their social media interaction with customers. Relevance and personalization of content are important to make consumers lifelong followers of a brand (Curran et al., 2018). Insights derived from an organization's increased interaction with its customers on social media could make the organization's communication more relevant, improve its products and service quality, enable faster and effective decisions, and create brand loyalty amongst its customers.

Social media is perceived as a low cost, widely used medium to transfer brand-related information and advertising to its social media savvy target customers. Companies and brands may view social media as a platform for sharing content that is informative, timely, and relevant, and entertainment worthy. Such timely communication can result in a positive consumer impression, involvement, as well as downstream actions such as purchase consideration and intent (Rohm et al., 2013). Organizations may use social media to regularly share their advertising campaigns, information related to their products and services, and other brands related information.

The results confirm that organizations believe in regularly collecting and analyzing customer comments, feedback, and suggestions for improving their existing products and services and creating new ones. Build on the foundation of customer insights, accessing knowledge, collecting ideas and concepts from users, and supporting new product launches, social media has come to be a strong resource for innovation and new product development (Roberts and Piller, 2016).

Social media particularly plays a significant role in developing product and brand awareness and brand equity (Zahoor et al., 2017). Social media allows organizations to personalize and target communication campaigns precisely and effectively. This research confirms a positive and strong impact of social media on marketing communications.

7. CONCLUSION

Through exploratory, quantitative research, the study extended U&G theory at the organizational level. The study confirms the importance of social media communication in prompting the organization to adopt social media. On the other hand, social media interaction does not play a direct role in influencing social media adoption for organizations as it does for individuals. For organizations, just interacting with their customers may not be a motivation to adopt a social media platform as they cannot control the outcome of these interactions to be always positive. However, these interactions allow the organizations to gather customer intelligence which can be useful for product/service design and improvement and to enhance the customer communication quality. One interesting observation is that social media interaction, not for itself but through perceived usefulness, becomes important for organizations.

In comparison to the number of studies available on social media adoption by individuals, research available on social media adoption by organizations is limited. This study contributes to the limited TAM & TOE based social media research from the organizational perspective. The research has also established a relationship between factors from TAM and U&G with social media interaction identified as a predictor for social media usefulness.

The findings of this research can enable marketing practitioners to leverage factors of top management support, interaction, communication, usefulness, and playfulness to adopt social media platforms that improve their marketing performance and brand image. Top management support in creating a social media strategy that is congruent with the business strategy, timely allocation of resources, setting-up a well-defined social media organizational structure, and escalation procedure are important to get strategic gains from social media. Also, integrating social media processes with the rest of the organization would increase the effectiveness and responsiveness of the firm.

When social media managers communicate more easily, effectively, and frequently with their online target audience, the

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chances of adoption of social media platforms by them increase. Sharing up-to-date information regularly, designing messaging which is personalized, interesting, entertaining, and engaging, and analyzing the feedback to improve products and services would be important for customer engagement. And as the bond between the company and its customers strengthens, customer satisfaction and sales growth would continue to increase (Shanahan et al., 2019).

Effective social media implementation will result in rich, relevant insights. Using AI, analysis of social media big data could reveal the psychographic characteristics of its customers that can be a valuable source of insight for marketers for enhancing user experience, innovation, and new product development efforts (Paschen et al., 2019). Data insights captured through social media interactions could further be used for decision making, future campaigns, and product and service innovation giving a competitive edge for the organization. Managers can leverage social media platforms by creating social communities that encourage ideas for improvements and innovation. Creating pages, forums, or blogs for their loyal customers to share ideas and brainstorm would be a good starting point. Dell's IdeaStorm and Starbucks MyStarbucksIdea are good examples of using social media to increase customer engagement and generate innovative ideas.

Limitations and Future Directions

While this study extends U&G theory at the organization level, additional confirmatory research in this area would give more insights for the managers to exploit and leverage social media. Social media's impact on marketing was studied on two factors of marketing communication and product and service development and improvement. This model can be extended by adding more factors to study the impact of social media adoption on marketing. Lastly, there can be a possibility of response bias as a single response per organization was taken in this research. Future studies can take more than one response per organization to mitigate this risk.

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APPENDIX 1

TABLE: XI

Summary of All Constructs and Measurement Items		
Latent Constructs	Measurement Items	Key References
Top management support (TMS)	TMS1: Formalizing Social Media Strategy	Researcher's own
	TMS2: Willingness to take risks	Adapted from Wang et al (2010)
	TMS3: Integrating social media processes	Researcher's own
	TMS4: Defining social media roles and responsibilities	Adapted from Tan et al (2007)
Social Media Perceived Usefulness (SMPU)	SMPU1: Improving effectiveness of the marketing team	Adapted from Chen & Wells (1999); Davis (1989); Venkatesh & Davis (2000)
	SMPU2: Staying in touch with target customers	Adapted from Chen & Wells (1999); Davis (1989)
	SMPU3: Better decision making	Adapted from Davis (1989); Venkatesh & Davis (2000); Lorenzo-Romero et al. (2014)
	SMPU4: Competitor Information on their social media strategies	Researcher's own
Social Media Perceived Playfulness (SMPP)	SMPP1: Features that are enjoyable	Adapted Chen et al. (2002); Korgaonkar & Wolin (1999); Chiang (2013)
	SMPP2: Fun element of social media	Adapted from Chen et al. (2002); Korgaonkar & Wolin (1999); Chiang (2013)
	SMPP3: Features that are exciting for customers	Adapted from Chen et al. (2002); Korgaonkar & Wolin (1999)
Social Media Interaction (SMI)	SMI1: Daily interactions with customers	Adapted from Grainger (2010)
	SMI2: Interaction amongst target customers	Adapted from Chen et al. (2002)
	SMI3: Facility to upload of audio-visual files	Adapted from Nair (2011)
	SMI4: Taking regular feedback	Researcher's own
Social Media Communication (SMC)	SMC1: Advertising campaigns	Researcher's own
	SMC2: Products and services communication	Researcher's own
	SMC3: Assessing customer satisfaction with communication	Researcher's own
	SMC4: Providing up-to- date information	Researcher's own
Social Media Adoption (SMADT)	SMADT1: Expansion of critical mass	Researcher's own
	SMADT2: Competitive pressure	Adapted from Wang et al (2010); Hsiu-Fen et al. (2008)

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	SMADT3: Competitive disadvantage	Adapted from Wang et al (2010); Hsiu-Fen et al. (2008); Lin et al (2008)
Product / Service Development and Improvement (PSDI)	PSDI1: Ideas for existing product and service improvement	Researcher's own
	PSDI2: Communication about introduction of existing products and service improvements	Researcher's own
	PSDI3: Feedback on existing products and service improvement	Researcher's own
	PSDI4: Ideas for new products and services design	Researcher's own
	PSDI5: Communication about introduction of new products and services	Researcher's own
	PSDI6: Feedback on new products and services	Researcher's own
Marketing Communication (MC)	MC1: Advertising campaigns effectiveness	Researcher's own
	MC2: Special offer campaigns effectiveness	Researcher's own
	MC3: Direct marketing campaigns effectiveness	Researcher's own
	MC4: Customer engagement effectiveness	Researcher's own
	MC5: Brand image	Researcher's own